

One-step extraction of key-value information from personal cards: automatic indexing of a 1940 Paris police control file.

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The *Préfecture de Police* control file is one of the files relating to the census and internment of Jews organized in France during the Second World War between 1940 and 1944. It was set up following the new census of Jews in October 1941. Its initial purpose was solely to monitor the population residing in the Seine department. This file is part of a set of documents officially deposited with the Shoah Memorial in December 1997 and kept in an enclave of the French Nationales Archives.

This control file consists of 31577 personal cards organized alphabetically into 27 directories. Each card contains information on one adult: identity (surname, first names, date and place of birth, sex, nationality), family situation and children, administrative and professional situation, official document numbers. Handwritten notes specify the dates and conditions of arrest and deportation. In total, the file concerns almost 40,000 people, since the names of children under 15 appear on their parents' files.

The image shows two personal cards from the control file. The left card is blue and for a French citizen, and the right card is yellow and for a foreigner. Both cards contain personal information such as name, date and place of birth, sex, nationality, profession, address, family situation, and children. The right card has handwritten notes in red and blue ink, including 'Arresté le 16-1-42' and 'COURM-297'.

Field	French Citizen (Left)	Foreigner (Right)
NOM	ADLER	EKL née Eklajaj
PRÉNOMS	Suzette	Sura
Date et lieu de naissance	25/1/05 à BUCAREST	1890 à Varsovie
N° du Dossier juif	27167	56469
SEXE	MAGE	féminin
NATIONALITE	FRANCAISE	polonaise
PROFESSION	ouvrière-houillère	sans
ADRESSE	42 Bd Soufflot PARIS	52 rue de Ménilmontant
SITUATION de famille	MARIÉ	marié
CONJOINT	JULIE	juif
ENFANTS de moins de 15 ans et à charge	MARIEA 13/4/26	Amjess 1927
SERVICES de GUERRE	1914-18	
REMARQUES PARTICULIÈRES	CAMP DE DRANCY	

Figure 1: Examples of 2 personal cards from the control file. Blue cards were used for French citizens (left) and yellow for foreigners (right). @Mémorial de la Shoah/ Archives Nationales de France

This file is used on a daily basis by the staff of the *Mémorial de la Shoah* to respond to tracing requests from families, but also to complete the life histories of Jews who were arrested, interned and deported from France between 1942 and 1944. However, its use is limited, as

it can only be consulted by name. Capturing all the information contained on these cards will not only make it easier to research individuals but will also enable historians to research information that is difficult to use today. The cards contain addresses, occupations, disabilities, war service, as well as the date and service that made the arrest.

Automatic information extraction

Despite the standardized nature of the initial document, the information recorded on these forms is highly variable: it may be in printed, typewritten or handwritten and the information can be detailed, partial, absent, or even in the wrong section. It was therefore necessary to choose an automatic information extraction model capable of adapting to this great diversity and taking into account the entire content of the forms in order to localize, recognize and type the information. We therefore chose an end-to-end key-value extraction system [1, 2]. This type of system has the advantage of being able to train directly on the information extracted in tabular form, without the need for a complete and localized transcript of the documents.

Figure 2 shows a personal card with the following information:

Key	Value
Name	SCHLESINGER
First name	Berthold
Date of Birth	11/02/1879
Place of birth	Prague
File number	24470
Sex	Masculin
Nationality	Tchécoslovaque
Occupation	Sans

Figure 2: Example of a tabular annotation of a personal card. The annotation consists of a set of key-value pairs, without the location on the image. @Mémorial de la Shoah/ Archives Nationales de France

A set of 496 documents (1.5% of the total) was manually annotated using the Callico open-source platform [3]. This annotation involves filling in a form with the information shown on the image. It is not necessary to indicate the position of the information on the image, which reduces the workload. The annotation was carried out by 5 people, at a pace of 3 minutes 20 per form (median), for a total of 26 hours.

Figure 3 : The Callico open-source annotation platform for key-value annotation. @Mémorial de la Shoah/ Archives Nationales de France.

After creating the set of annotated documents, we train the information extraction model using an open-source version of the DAN library [5]. Once the annotated data was available, the training was carried out in less than 2 working days thanks to the integration of the DAN library into the Arkindex platform. The model can extract the requested information directly from the image, bypassing the intermediate stages of text line detection, Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR), and Named-Entity Recognition (NER). In addition, the position of the information on the image can be determined by observing where the model focuses its attention when predicting each piece of information.

Figure 4 : Recognition of a complete index card with an end-to-end model: the model detects the text, recognises it and types the information using a named entity formalism. The link between the text and the image can be deduced from the attention of the model.

After analyzing the automatic extraction results on an independent test set, we have identified that the model's performance was much better on the civil status information,

located at the top of the document. This result can be explained by the fact that this part is the best filled in and the most standardized. Entries concerning arrest, for example, are much more variable and unsystematic. It was therefore decided to group all information other than civil status into a single free text field. The performance of the model, in terms of Character Error Rate (CER), for each type of information is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Character Error Rate (CER) for the main fields of the card, estimated on an independent test set. The most common and stable information is best recognised (surname, date of birth, spouse/partner, gender, first name).

Field	CER (%)
Surname	0,25
Date of birth	0,56
Spouse/husband	1,59
Gender	1,97
First name	2,37
File number	3,39
Nationality	3,73
Address	5,45
Occupation	7,16
Marital status	8,33
Place of birth	11,71
children under 15	13,52

All the records were processed automatically using the Arkindex [4] document processing platform, and the results were sent to the Callico platform for manual validation of the least recognized information. This task is carried out in collaboration with the French National Archives by a team of around ten people. We decided to re-read/validate the automatically recognized information before making it available to the public, as these documents are often among the last traces of people who disappeared in the Shoah. We felt it was imperative that the information communicated should be as close to reality as possible, even if it is always possible to return to the original digitized document.

Example of data analysis

This initial indexing of the collection makes it possible to explore the main trends in the data, such as the nationalities of the deportees, their occupations and the mapping of their addresses in Paris, thus providing a basic understanding of the demographic landscape.

necessary to reduce the residual error rate. In all cases, automatic processing makes it possible to initiate an indexing process which, without automation, would be considered insurmountable, too long or too costly.

References

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